

Oxidation of Dimethylamine by Diperio-dato-nickelate(IV) in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

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The title reaction is found to be first order in [DPN] (DPN, diperio-datonickelate(IV)) and fractional order both in [DMA] (DMA, diamethylamine) and [OH⁻]. Periodate causes retradation. Effects of added products, ionic strength, dielectric constant and temperature on the oxidation kinetics have been studied. MPN (monoperio-datonickelate(IV)) was found to be the active form of oxidant. A tentative mechanism with complex formation between MPN and DMA followed by the decomposition into products is proposed. The rate law which follows from the mechanism is derived.

The use of nickel(IV) complexes as oxidants in the form of nickel(IV) oxime and nickel(IV) periodate¹ is limited to a few cases. Nickel(IV) periodate oxidation of aliphatic amines, alcohols, acids and acetophenones in alkaline medium have been studied². The studies involving nickel(IV) periodate oxidation are limited by the fact that its solubility and stability in aqueous solution are very low. Mechanistically oxidation with nickel(IV) as oxidant are expected to involve the possibility of intervention of nickel(III) and this is not expected in case of a complementary two-equivalent oxidation reaction. Indeed, stable nickel(III) complexes are known³. Again multiple equilibria involving different nickel(IV) periodate complexes prevail in an alkaline solution² and it needs to know the active form of the oxidant in the reaction.

The oxidation of the simplest dialkylamine, i.e. diamethylamine (DMA) is limited by the fact that it is gas at ordinary temperature. A few attempts have been made in gaseous medium⁴ to oxidise DMA but no studies seem to be available in alkaline medium. Amines are easily oxidised but the product obtained depends upon the oxidising agent. In view of these reasons, we have sought to study the oxidation of the simplest dialkylamine, namely DMA. The oxidation of DMA by diperio-datonickelate(IV) (DPN) is

feasible in aqueous alkaline medium and it can be conveniently followed spectrophotometrically. In the present study, we attempt to understand the mechanism of DPN-DMA reaction in alkaline medium as well as the active form of nickel(IV) periodate complex.

Results and Discussion

The order of the reaction was found by log initial rate versus log concentration plots by varying the concentration of oxidant reductant and alkali in turn, while keeping the other constant (Table 1). The order in [DPN] was unity and the order in [DMA] ~ 0.5 and the order in [OH⁻] ~ 0.8. Prior addition of reaction products and sulphate and nitrate did not affect the reaction rate. However chloride retards the reaction presumably due to a particular salt-effect, chloride being compact and highly electronegative and capable of manifesting a particular effect via a hydrogen bond. Added periodate decreased the rate. The order in [IO₄⁻] is ~ 0.9. Ionic strength effect is negligibly small and decrease in dielectric constant enhanced the rate.

With the condition [DPN] = 2.65×10^{-5} , [DMA] = 6.25×10^{-6} , [OH⁻] = 0.25 and [IO₄⁻] = 2.25×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ the kinetic runs were carried out at 298, 303, 308, 313 and 318 K.

The approximate second order rate constant (k) obtained are 13.9, 25.6, 83.3, 111 and 190 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$ respectively. The value of k is obtained as the slope of the plot $1/(a-x)$ vs t , where a is the initial concentration of DPN and x the change in concentration of DPN in time (t). The activation parameters E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were found to be $118.5 (\pm 5) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-164 (\pm 8) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The rate law for the title reaction follows from experimental results as in equation (1),

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k [\text{DPN}] [\text{DMA}]^{0.5} [\text{OH}^-]^{0.8}}{[\text{IO}_4^-]^{0.9}} \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [DPN], [DMA], [OH⁻] AND [IO₄⁻] on DPN-DMA REACTION

Temp. = 25°, $I = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[DPN] $\times 10^5$ mol dm^{-3}	[DMA] $\times 10^5$ mol dm^{-3}	[OH ⁻] $\times 10$ mol dm^{-3}	[IO ₄ ⁻] $\times 10^4$ mol dm^{-3}	Initial rate, $\times 10^8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
				Exptl.	Calcd.
1.53	1.25	2.0	4.3	4.8	5.7
2.73	1.25	2.0	4.3	9.1	10.3
3.49	1.25	2.0	4.3	14.4	13.2
4.85	1.25	2.0	4.3	18.1	18.4
5.20	1.25	2.0	4.3	20.8	20.0
5.92	1.25	2.0	4.3	25.6	26.0
5.20	0.40	2.0	4.3	10.2	8.6
5.20	0.80	2.0	4.3	15.8	14.8
5.20	1.25	2.0	4.3	20.6	20.0
5.20	1.60	2.0	4.3	24.0	23.0
5.20	2.00	2.0	4.3	26.0	26.0
5.20	1.25	1.0	4.3	12.5	13.0
5.20	1.25	1.2	4.3	14.5	15.0
5.20	1.25	1.4	4.3	15.0	16.8
5.20	1.25	1.6	4.3	17.8	18.0
5.20	1.25	1.8	4.3	18.1	19.1
5.20	1.25	2.0	4.3	20.1	20.0
5.20	1.25	2.0	4.3	20.8	20.0
5.20	1.25	2.0	6.3	15.4	16.0
5.20	1.25	2.0	8.3	12.8	13.0
5.20	1.25	2.0	10.3	10.9	11.4
5.20	1.25	2.0	12.3	8.8	9.9
5.20	1.25	2.0	14.3	7.7	8.8

The water-soluble Ni^{IV} periodate complex is reported⁵ to be $[\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6)]^{2-}$. Although periodate is involved in multiple equilibria which prevail to varying extents depending on the pH

employed under the conditions of high pH of 13.3 of this study, the form which predominates is understood to be the species, $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ (as present in the Ni^{IV} complex)⁵. The results of rate increase with increase of alkalinity and the rate decrease with increase of periodate concentration (Table 1) suggests that equilibria of different Ni^{IV} periodate complexes matter. It may be expected, monoperiodatonickelate(IV) (MPN) is more important in the reaction than diperiodatonickelate(IV) (DPN).

The effect of [IO₄⁻] on the rate might be due to the equilibria between DPN, MPN and IO₄⁻ in alkaline medium (equations 2 and 3 of

Fig. 1. Verification of rate law (6) in the form of equation (6a) (conditions same as in Table 1).

Scheme 1). Added acrylamide monomer did not undergo polymerisation under inert atmosphere indicating the absence of free radical formation in the reaction mixture. The fractional order in substrate (DMA), presumably results from a complex formation between the oxidant and substrate prior to the formation of products. Indeed, it is to be noted that the plot of $1/\text{rate}$ vs $1/[\text{DMA}]$ shows an intercept in agreement with such a complex formation. These results indicate a mechanism of the type presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (6), K_1 , K_2 and K_3 being the constants of different equilibria and k is the rate constant of the decomposition of complex C,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= - \frac{d[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} \\ &= \frac{k K_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-] [\text{DMA}]}{\{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1 [\text{OH}^-] [\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_1 K_2 [\text{OH}^-] + K_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{DMA}] [\text{OH}^-]\}} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Equation (6) may be rearranged into the form (6a) which is suitable for verification,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{DMA}]_{\text{T}}}{\text{Rate}} &= \\ &= \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{k K_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{k K_2 K_3} + \frac{1}{k K_3} + \frac{[\text{DMA}]}{k} \quad (6a) \end{aligned}$$

Other conditions being constant plots of $[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{DMA}]_{\text{T}} / \text{Rate}$ against each $1/[\text{OH}^-]$, $[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]$ and $[\text{DMA}]$ should be linear as is actually found (Fig. 1). From the slopes and intercepts, the values of K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and k could be derived as $1.00 (\pm 0.05) \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $4.20 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 2 \times 10^{-5}) \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $3.30 \times 10^5 (\pm 4 \times 10^3) \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ and $0.0104 (\pm 0.001) \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. Using these constants, calculated rates are in good agreement with the experimental rates (Table 1) which fortifies the reaction scheme.

The observed increase in the rate of reaction with decrease in polarity of the reaction medium is that expected for a reaction between an ion and a neutral molecule. The observed negligibly small

effect of ionic strength on the reaction is presumably due to the fact that the reaction is between an ion and a neutral molecule (Scheme 1). The complex involved in the mechanism is expected to lead to a sizable negative entropy of activation and this is found to be the case in the reaction.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals and double-distilled water used. A 40% aqueous DMA solution (Loba Chemie) was distilled using ice-cold water and its strength was ascertained by titrating against standard hydrochloric acid using methylorange indicator. To carry out the kinetic runs freshly diluted and standardised DMA solution of required concentration was used. The solid DPN complex was prepared by a standard procedure⁶. Aqueous solution of DPN (1.0 mol dm^{-3}) was obtained by dissolving the solid complex in aqueous alkaline medium at 50° . The nickel(IV) complex in alkaline solution was determined gravimetrically after reducing the Ni^{IV} to Ni^{II} and precipitating Ni^{II} as the dimethylglyoxime complex. Potassium hydroxide and potassium nitrate were employed to maintain the required alkalinity and ionic strength respectively, in the reaction solution.

Kinetic runs were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ unless otherwise mentioned. The progress of the reaction was followed by mixing the previously thermostated reactant solutions of DPN and DMA which also contained the required amount of potassium nitrate. The reaction mixture was then placed in a 1 cm quartz cell and the absorbance of solution at 410 nm was monitored at different intervals of time on a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer. DPN concentrations between 1.0×10^{-5} to 2×10^{-4} in 0.2 mol dm^{-3} alkali obeyed Beer's law with molar absorption coefficient as $7500 \pm 375 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The kinetic runs were followed under second order conditions and could be reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Stoichiometry : Different reaction mixtures containing different concentrations of DPN and DMA with constant alkali concentration (0.20 mol dm^{-3}) were kept for about 6 h and then analysed. The concentration of DPN was estimated by spectrophotometry, while nickel(II) was analysed as

the dimethylglyoxime complex gravimetrically. Other main products, formate and ammonia were characterised by spot test⁷ and Nessler's reagent test⁸ respectively. The results showed 1 : 4 stoichiometry.

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